

RESPONSE TO PERFORMANCE 2023 SUBMISSION #81

We greatly appreciate the reviewers’ constructive comments and positive evaluations towards this paper. We will definitely incorporate them (e.g., adding more related work, polishing the statements to avoid confusion, highlighting the contributions, and including the additional experimental results) into our revision. We answer the shepherd’s questions as follows.

Q1: Are the assumptions made for theoretical analysis limiting in terms of practical applications?

A1: While the assumptions (Assumptions 1-3) are necessary for theoretical analysis, they are also practical in microservice systems (potentially other computer systems).

Assumption 1 states the reward and constraint functions are continuous and bounded. These are typically mild and usually true in microservice systems as shown in Figure 1; Assumption 3 states there always exists a feasible policy/configuration such that SLA constraints are strictly satisfied. This assumption is necessary and also reflects the reality of real systems. Without such an assumption/condition, the resource configuration optimization could be impossible and it suggests that the system manager has to increase the resource capacity; Assumption 2 states the observation noises are i.i.d sub-Gaussian. While it is consistent with our observations in the experiments, we acknowledge that it could be a potential issue in computer systems where the latency has a heavy-tailed phenomenon.

Fig. 1: Uncertain latency-resource relationship (Figure 1a in the paper).

Q2: How scalable is the approach?

A2: We discuss POBO’s scalability from two folds, i.e., fully-distributed implementation and the algorithm’s complexity. For the fully-distributed implementation on top of multiple servers, POBO can be extended easily when pods of one identical service are implemented on one server. For example, the pods of the login service are all implemented on Server 1, the pods of the search service are all implemented on Server 2, etc. In this case, POBO can learn the latency-resource function well and give the optimal resource configuration without modification. However, when pods of one particular service are implemented on different servers, the latency-resource function cannot be learned since the requests’ latencies are not solely based on the number of pods. For example, the login service is implemented on both Server 1 and 2. The workload generator and the Server 1 are connected by the LAN network, and the workload generator and the Server 2 are connected by the WAN network. In this case, it is essential to consider various network conditions among multiple servers when learning login requests’ latencies.

For the time complexity, if we increase the number of requests and the maximum number of pods, the computation time of getting the resource configuration in each period increases linearly. In our experiment, compared with the execution time to handle the requests, the computation time is negligible, thus making the algorithm scalable.

Q3: Nonstationary was addressed in terms of the request mix, but what about in terms of the total number of arrivals?

A3: This is a great suggestion. We tested our algorithm with a daily workload pattern extracted from real-world data collected in the production environment [R1]. As shown in Figure 2, the traffic is highly non-stationary (including original and interpolated data points). We plot the results in Figure 2 and it is shown that POBO outperforms CKB and HPA on the three evaluation metrics. As requested by reviewer C in **Q7**, we also provide the results of customized RPOL. We observe that RPOL is aggressive in satisfying SLAs and usually uses more pods than POBO. It is interesting to observe that RPOL works better in non-stationary traffic than the stationary ones in **Q7** and we conjecture the possible reason is due to its aggressive design. We will include these results and discussion in the revision.

Fig. 2: Daily workload pattern extracted and interpolated from [R1].

(a) Average number of used pods.

(b) Percentage of violated requests.

(c) P90 tail latency.

Fig. 3: The experimental results with non-stationary workload pattern in Fig. 2.

Q4: What setting for HPA was used? Were they optimized in any way?

A4: We apologize for the confusion and will clarify HPA’s setting in the revision. HPA provides a configurable parameter, i.e., the target resource utilization. HPA calculates the ratio α of the current resource utilization over the target resource utilization during runtime. HPA sets the newly adjusted pod number to the rounded value of $(\alpha \times \text{the current pod number})$. In our experiment, we set the target CPU utilization to 60% by default. A lower target CPU utilization can result in more pods, a lower percentage of violated requests, and a smaller tail latency, and vice versa. However, HPA’s scaling strategy targets at optimizing resource utilization which is not adaptive to the requests’ latencies. To optimize the latencies with HPA, we need to know the latency-resource relationship, which is exactly the research problem we want to address.

Q5: How generalizable are the results over different kinds of workloads?

A5: We believe POBO is general and could be adaptive to most types of workloads because it learns the black-box functions (e.g., the latency-resource functions) from scratch and adjusts the resource configuration in real-time. However, we acknowledge that for the workloads with heavy-tail property (related to **Q1**), we might need to customize the design of POBO to tackle the specific challenge.

Q6: Why is the chosen kernel the correct one? Were other choices considered, for example, a Matern kernel or even a dynamic kernel?

A6: The reason that we choose Squared Exponential (SE) kernel in our experiments is based on the belief of inherent “smoothness” (i.e., the latency-resource relation is smooth), where SE can capture the “smoothness” well and introduce minimal bias (see Chapter 5 in [R2]).

As the reviewer mentioned, Matérn kernel is another default choice in Gaussian processes. It is more general than the SE kernel to some extent because it can capture the potential “non-smoothness” property. However, in our setting, we believe these two kernels would not make any difference as the inherent “smoothness” illustrated in Figure 1. To verify this, we tested POBO under SE and Matérn kernel, respectively. The results are in Figure 4 and it is shown that they are almost identical as we expected.

Finally, we appreciate the reviewer for the great suggestion on incorporating dynamic kernels in POBO. This would definitely improve our algorithm in the dynamic environment and we leave it in our future research.

Fig. 4: The experimental results comparing SE kernel and Matern kernel.

Q7: Why were comparisons not made to RPOL [14], rather than CKB [27]? This may be more reasonable as low tail probabilities are more likely to imply a low average than vice-versa.

A7: We did not incorporate RPOL in our previous version because the setting is slightly off for RPOL where RPOL is suitable for SLA on the tail latency and our setting considers SLAs on both the average system latency and the tail latency for the critical requests. There exist two issues in applying RPOL: 1) it is unclear how to properly set the threshold of the tail latency to satisfy the average system latency constraint; 2) RPOL might behave aggressively (or over-conservatively in satisfying SLAs).

We customize RPOL for our setting by imposing various tail latencies and the results are summarized in Figures 5-7. The results justify our intuition that a tight threshold leads to a low percentage of violated requests but might introduce the conservative resource configuration in Figure 5; and a loose threshold leads to a proper configuration but results in a large tail latency and a larger percentage of violated requests in Figure 6. The observation is also similar even when we set different thresholds for three types of requests in Figure 7.

Fig. 5: RPOL's target tail latency for all the requests is set to 400ms.

Fig. 6: RPOL's target tail latency for all the requests is set to 1000ms.

Fig. 7: RPOL’s target tail latencies for login/search/recommendation requests are set to 400/700/1000ms.

Q8: The explanation of the $O(\sqrt{T})$ regret/violation for the tail is confusing (what does it mean “for almost ...”, given the underlying function of T ?)

A8: Recall that the definition $G^+(c_t, x_t)$ denotes the violation of tail latency for the request c_t with the configuration x_t . The result of $\mathcal{V}_{tail}(T) = O(\sqrt{T})$ implies the violation (per request) is $O(1/\sqrt{T})$. In other words, it means the tail latency requirement can always be satisfied under our algorithm for a large T . Hope this can address the reviewer’s concern and we will clarify it in the revision.

Q9: Does the fundamentally different dynamics of Q and \hat{Q} has directly influence the corresponding $O(1)$ and $O(\sqrt{T})$? If yes, the obvious question is why doesn’t \hat{Q} follow the same dynamic as Q ?

A9: The careful design in the dynamics of Q and \hat{Q} leads to the theoretical result, i.e., $\mathcal{V}_{ave}(T) = O(1)$ average violation and $\mathcal{V}_{tail}(T) = O(\sqrt{T})$ hard violations, respectively. Note that the former metric can be compensated among different rounds while the latter one is non-compensatable. Intuitively, Q is dedicated to tracking and controlling the constraint violations *over the long term*, while \hat{Q} is designed (as the strict penalty term) to satisfy the tail latency constraint *anytime*. Applying the same design of Q to \hat{Q} does not guarantee a small hard violation or *anytime* satisfactory for tail latency constraint.

Reference

[R1] Qizhen Weng, et al. “MLaaS in the Wild: Workload Analysis and Scheduling in Large-Scale Heterogeneous GPU Clusters”. In *19th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI)*, 2022.

[R2] Carl Edward Rasmussen and Christopher K. I. Williams. “Gaussian Processes for Machine Learning”. *The MIT Press*, 2006.